

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE RESTORATION OF THE CROWN PART OF THE TOOTH WITH CERAMIC AND ZIRCONIUM VENEERS

Musayeva H.H.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, associate professor
Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Orthopedic Dentistry
Baku, Azerbaijan*

Abstract

The article aims to consider the advantages and disadvantages of using veneers in modern cosmetic dentistry. Veneers are ultra-thin ceramic (porcelain) or composite resin shells bonded to the front of the teeth and are an excellent alternative to crowns in many situations. They provide a much more conservative approach to changing the color, size, or shape of a tooth. They can also mask unwanted imperfections such as tetracycline-stained teeth and damage due to trauma or root canal procedures.

Keywords: veneers, veneering, ceramic veneers, cosmetic dentistry.

Among dental diseases, the pathology of hard dental tissues is the most common. The indicators of the need for their treatment among the population are largely associated with the high prevalence of caries and non-carious lesions of the teeth, as well as the lack of motivation in patients for the prevention and treatment of this pathology [6]. When treating anterior teeth, aesthetics and durability of restorations are the main requirements. Thanks to modern filling materials and technologies, these tasks are quite feasible.[1] But it is necessary to take into account the indications and contraindications, the type of pathology, the age of the patient, the indicators of general somatic polymorbidity, it is reasonable to choose the filling material and the method of treatment, to follow the rules for the preparation of hard dental tissues, taking into account the pathological process and the restoration technique [2].

Priority in dentistry are high technologies, which include the method of direct veneer of anterior teeth with light-cured composites. An indication for the use of direct veneering (veneer) is a defect in the hard tissues of the tooth from 1/3 to 1/2 of the volume of the crown, the need to correct the shape, color or position of the tooth [4]. It is known that with the help of veneer it is easier to achieve a good aesthetic result and the long-term data on this indicator are better in comparison with the traditional method of aesthetic restoration of teeth using even the most modern light-curing composite filling materials [5].

In therapeutic dentistry, direct aesthetic restoration of teeth using modern light-curing composite filling materials is most often used. The main indications for its implementation are the need to restore the aesthetic and functional parameters of the tooth in the treatment of caries and its complications, non-carious lesions of the teeth, as well as the correction of the aesthetic parameters of the tooth. Contraindications are divided into absolute and relative [7].

Veneers allow you to achieve a high aesthetic result with a change in tooth color and the presence of defects in the tooth surface. In the process of vital activity, a variety of organic and inorganic dyes affect the teeth, which can affect the teeth in different ways: some dyes are deposited only on the surface of the teeth,

some penetrate into hard tissues (enamel, dentin). Veneers have become the best option for aesthetic prosthetics of the anterior group of teeth. Their manufacture does not affect the adjacent periodontal tissues, which is very important. Modern materials used in the manufacture of ceramic and zirconia veneers are inorganic substances and compounds such as: porcelain (ceramic) and zirconia. Porcelain is a vitreous ceramic material, smooth and completely impenetrable. Zirconium dioxide is a naturally occurring zirconium compound that has been used in orthopedic dentistry for 10-15 years. It is partially stabilized with yttrium and also enriched with aluminum. This gives it such positive characteristics as bending strength (> 1400 MPa*) and rigidity [8].

Purpose: To study the properties of ceramic and zirconium veneers, their advantages and disadvantages.

Veneers are a metal-free method of prosthetics. The absence of a metal frame in them allows you to increase the aesthetics of the dentition. The light that hits the veneer can penetrate to different depths of the material and be reflected from the tissues of the tooth, so the veneer will not be any different from neighboring teeth.

Ceramic veneers. They are made of ceramics by an indirect method in dental laboratories. Ceramic materials for veneers can be divided into several groups:

- 1) cast glass ceramics
- 2) hot pressing ceramics
- 3) traditional ceramics based on feldspar.

Porcelain veneers are used in various cases, most often - the elimination of small defects or chips in the anterior teeth. In addition, they are often used to eliminate diastemas, correct the shape and position of the tooth.

The main advantages of ceramic veneers include:

1. Resistance to staining with dyes. When using photocurable materials, after eating, which has any dyes, their color changes over time, and stains appear on the teeth. Unlike them, ceramic veneers are resistant to dyes, since the surface of such a veneer is smooth and impenetrable, this is determined by the properties of ceramics. Therefore, spots do not appear on their surface.

2. Strength, durability. Porcelain veneers are highly durable and resistant to abrasion and wear.

3. Aesthetics. Veneers are color stable, it is possible to choose and modify their color, shape, fluorescent effect of ceramics.

4. Biocompatibility with surrounding tissues. Plaque builds up less on ceramic surfaces

But ceramic veneers also have their drawbacks. Due to medical errors (underestimation of occlusal factors, occlusal plane, morphology of the chewing surface of the teeth, hypertonicity and hyperactivity of the chewing muscles, improper preparation, etc.) and technical omissions, chipping of ceramic veneers and, under certain circumstances, even more serious complications, both aesthetic and functional, are possible, up to their complete loss [3]. But the frequency of unfixation and chipping of the veneer does not significantly depend on the type of tooth.

Zirconia veneers. One of the varieties of veneers, which are made from zirconium dioxide. Such veneers have the main feature - they are made in the same way in laboratories as ceramic veneers, but not by the hands of a technician, but by means of automated, fully robotic equipment - CAD / CAM. This avoids a number of errors.

Crowns based on ICE Zircon with reinforced veneer strength.

Such a crown made of zirconium dioxide has a high strength in places that are subjected to a higher masticatory load, as it has a thicker base layer from this one [4].

Unlike ceramic veneers, microprostheses based on zirconium dioxide are used even in the most difficult clinical cases. For example, if the color of the tooth is so changed that it can show through the ceramic, or there are large interdental spaces in the dentition, the teeth "find" each other, there are rotations of the tooth around its axis, etc. Zirconia is a very strong and lightweight material, so veneers based on it are thin [1].

The main advantages of zirconia veneers:

1. High biocompatibility with tooth tissues and adjacent tissues, which does not cause an allergic reaction.

2. High strength and reliability, no risk of chipping. This is ensured by the strength properties of zirconium dioxide - it is stronger and lighter than metal.

3. Durability, due to the above properties.

4. High aesthetics in the oral cavity. Zirconia veneers look like real natural teeth. Their aesthetics are preserved for a long time, since zirconia is not stained by various dyes.

There are not so many disadvantages of zirconium veneers, the main significant disadvantage is:

1. Unlike ceramic, they have a high cost, which is associated with the complexity of manufacturing zirconia veneers.

The success of the preparation of teeth for veneers requires minimal excision of the hard tissues of the teeth.

Conclusion

Thus, after analyzing scientific articles, we can conclude that ceramic veneers are undoubtedly one of the best options for restoring the frontal group of teeth and restoring their aesthetics. Zirconium dioxide stands out as the best material. With it, you can achieve the most natural color reproduction and light refraction. Microprostheses are less prone to chipping, fit snugly to the tooth tissues, which is the prevention of unfixation and the occurrence of secondary caries. But at the same time, there are also negative sides: the cost is much higher than similar porcelain restorations. Veneers occupy an important place in modern dentistry.

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